

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

ENGLISH OR RUSSIAN: which language is more important for a medical student to learn?

K.A.Abdurashidova

the teacher of English in Foreign Languages Department of ASMI

Jalolov A.A.

2nd year student of the Faculty of Dentistry of Andijan State Medical Institute

Annotation: This article is about how much English is necessary for students studying in higher educational institutions, especially medical students, and what opportunities and opportunities it creates.

Abstract: in this article we provide information on the role learning foreign language among medical students.

Key word: Russian, English, literature, systematize, knowledge, colleagues
Students who are just entering or studying in a medical institution have many questions. Among such questions is one of the most frequently repeated questions: "What language should I learn; Russian or English?". I want to answer this question based on my life experience. This article is primarily intended for medical students, but I hope it will be equally useful for students of other specialties. I understand very well the position of the student asking this question. Because I was in the same situation when I was a 1-2 year student. Russian or English? Which one should you start with? What's more important? I asked questions about which is easier and so on. When I was at school, I did not learn Russian or any

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

other foreign language, because we lived in the countryside and I went to a village school. Until the age of 18, I did not speak any other language except Uzbek, there are many doctors in my family. Everyone emphasized how important the Russian language is in medicine. All literature at home was in Russian.

Literature in English was incomparably different from literature in Russian or Uzbek that I had seen before. Literature in English was written in a very simple, understandable language and very systematized. The benefits were obvious. If it took me half an hour to understand the same topic from a book in English, I would spend more than an hour reading a book in Russian to understand the same topic. At that time, my level of knowledge of the English language was not much different from the level of my knowledge of the Russian language. I didn't know any of them very well. I couldn't speak in both. I could barely write in both. I could read and translate only with the help of a dictionary, and since it was easy for me to read and understand books in English, I began to read books and receive information only in English. I concluded: the medical language is English. For me, English has become the language of medicine. Below are the reasons for the advantages of English.

Reason 1. The language of the study is English. Medicine is a field rich in research. Medicine cannot develop without research. Research = development. More than 90% of researchers in the world work in English. The results of the study are published in English. The reason is simple! English is accepted as the international language. The researcher may be Uzbek, Chinese, Spanish or Russian, but he wants the results of his scientific work to be read by the whole world. So he tries to type in English. Colleagues devoted to Russian medicine are

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

discussing this. A number of articles are also published in Russian. If what you say is true, why would they do it? they speak English is the main language of science for influential Russian scientists and doctors or ambitious young Russian doctors. They read books and articles in English and try to publish their scientific papers in English.

Reason 2. The quantity and quality of literature in English is high. This is a direct continuation of the reason written above. It takes 17 years from the discovery of a medical discovery to its practical application. Medical books/textbooks are collections of scientific articles and new discoveries. This means that it takes at least 17 years to use an innovation in textbooks.

This happens when ministries of education and institutes train students in the latest methods of treatment. We all know it's not. That is why they say that medical textbooks and real practice are different. The reason for the difference is that textbooks are far behind. This problem exists in many countries. This is why medical students in developed countries study diseases by studying new scientific articles rather than books. The main reason for this is that it takes a long time to publish scientific articles in book form, and in addition, the results of most articles are never published in books. The printed ones also only appear in English-language books. Most of these books will never be translated into Russian. I will not be mistaken if I say that less than 5% has been translated. There is no translation into Uzbek. Many people remember that Soviet medicine was excellent. In Soviet medicine, there would be a lot of scientific research and research. Maybe Soviet medicine was really good (or maybe the best) in the world. I was interested to know how many articles were published in what language at that time, to test the

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

idea that there may have been many medical articles in Russian at that time. I was able to find only one article that compared literature published in different languages. At that time, the number of articles published in Russian was only 2% of articles published in medicine. About 40% was in English. Already in 1959 there were 20 times more articles in English. The conclusion is up to you. And I can say that this 2 percent figure has not increased.

3rd reason. Study and internship abroad. Knowledge of English makes it possible to continue studying abroad or improve qualifications in modern clinics. Grants can be won by knowing English. In this case, it will cover the cost of training or advanced training. Imagine that if you speak English, they will pay for your travel, accommodation, meals, tuition and additional personal expenses. These are not words from heaven. I speak from my personal experience. I'm not the only one. I know several dozen people.

Reason 4. English makes you competitive in your field. Allows you to become a famous doctor. Of course, not all of your fellow students study English or any other foreign language. Because there are too many lazy people. So tomorrow, when you become a doctor, you will directly "compete" with those who studied with you (or with a difference of +/- 10 years). In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the main indicator that determines how much money you can earn in the field of medicine is the number of your clients. The more clients, the more income. (!I am against the fact that the doctor worked for free and humiliated!) Now imagine this situation. A patient has come to you. You have been to 5 doctors without treatment because you were either misdiagnosed or treated in vain. You recently read an article about his illness and participated in a discussion in English with foreign

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

doctors (for example, in one of the groups for doctors on Facebook). It was on the basis of this new knowledge that you were able to diagnose and treat the patient. Once a patient is cured, there is no stronger doctor than you. Because he went to 5 before you and got no help. He found it with you. He says this to people every day. This is one of the most effective marketing methods in medicine. In English, this is called "word of mouth". In Uzbek: "So-and-so went, quickly recovered, recovered!" how to say. This situation determines the money you earn. More satisfied customers = more money (if desired). This is what gives you the ability to be stronger than the 5 doctors before you.

5. Work with evidence-based medicine. Having become acquainted with medicine in English, you will have an idea of how the whole world works, especially a number of medically developed countries (USA, European countries, India, etc.). You will gain knowledge in the field of evidence-based medicine. Then you start comparing. You can learn a lot by comparing.

BOSH_ADMIN, [10.11.2022 17:39]

Through comparisons like these, you'll understand why so many patients don't find treatment. These reasons can go on and on. This is not even one of the 10 reasons why what I have written will benefit you as a doctor. I am sure that English will help you not only become an educated doctor, but also become a person, get out of the shell, understand the people around you, the world. What I wrote does not mean that you should not learn Russian, just that English will help you more as a future doctor.

In short, English is one of the 5 languages approved by the UN for international

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

languages. Even for us, if I say an advantage, a person with 7.5 IELTS in English can easily go to Arab countries and there. He will not only increase his religious and worldly knowledge, but also get a good profitable job, besides, he will have time to gain experience in his field.

References

1. English-Uzbek electronic dictionary, Hasanboy Rasulov
2. 2. Wikipedia, an open encyclopedia
3. English grammar. Gapparov M, Kasimova R

